

Phenology and yield evaluation of hazelnut cultivars in Latium Region

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Abstract

In central Italy (Latium), hazelnut cultivation is carried out using only a few round-shaped nut producing cultivars including 'Tonda Gentile Romana', 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'Nocchione' as main pollinizer. With the aim to extend the hazelnut genetic base a variety collection was established in a typical hazelnut-growing area of Viterbo province. The collection consists of 48 cultivars, each represented by three multi-stemmed trees. Flowering time, female and male full bloom, leaf budbreak, and leaf fall of each cultivar were recorded over three years (2014-2016). Sucker production and vigor of the trees were also measured. Further, nut yield and nut and kernel traits were investigated. On average, 'Tonda Rossa', 'Karidaty', 'Sivri A' and 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe' showed a very early period of pollen shed, which was concentrated in the middle of December. In respect to female bloom, the earliest female bloom was in 'Nostrale', 'San Giovanni' and 'Tonda di Giffoni', which showed style emergence (red-dot stage) at the end of November. 'San Giovanni' and 'Tonda di Giffoni' showed also an early leaf budbreak, which occurred in mid-February, and this early vegetative growth could make this cultivar vulnerable to frost injury. 'Camponica' showed the highest yield over the period of investigation, and 'Nociara' showed the highest yield efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

Hazelnut is an important fruit tree crop grown in temperate climates, and about 30 cultivars currently represent the basis of worldwide hazelnut production (Mehlenbacher, 2009). In Italy, a limited number of cultivars are grown in the major production regions. In Piedmont, production is mainly of 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe', and in Latium it is mainly of 'Tonda Gentile Romana' with 'Nocchione' as pollinizer (Cristofori et al., 2008).

Recently, in many Italian rural areas new hazelnut orchards have been established using Differential Global Navigation Satellite System – Real Time Kinematic (DGNSS-RTK) for designing and mechanically planting single trunk high density plantations (Cristofori et al., 2017). Nevertheless, little consideration is given to choice of cultivar and its adaptation to local environmental conditions, only a few Italian cultivars with round nuts are planted. Many production areas in Italy show a narrow genetic base, which makes the orchards vulnerable to pest and disease attacks and injury from frost or drought. For example, in Viterbo province “moria” syndrome caused by a bacterium (Scortichini et al., 1994, Varvaro et al., 1994) led farmers to replace 'Tonda Gentile Romana' in the damaged orchards with 'Tonda di Giffoni' as the latter was believed to be less susceptible to the disease.

Furthermore, several researchers have observed variation in the behavior of the hazelnut cultivars when grown under different microclimate conditions (Baldwin et al., 2001; Turcu

et al., 2001; Santos et al., 2005; Solar and Stampar, 2011). The sensitivity of most cultivars to environmental factors may lead to different performance when they are introduced to new areas.

For these reasons and in order to propose an enlargement of the genetic base of hazelnut orchards in Latium, recently a collection field was established in the basin of Vico Lake in Viterbo province (Cristofori et al., 2014), including many cultivars currently grown in the major hazelnut crop areas. Observations on phenology and vegetative and productive traits were carried out over the period 2014-2016.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

In the year 2000 the collection was established by ARSIAL and Centro di Ricerca per la Frutticoltura (Roma) in a typical hazelnut-growing area of Viterbo province (Italy), at "Le Cese" near Vico Lake, on a sandy clay loam soil with pH 6.1, 2.2% organic matter and a low total calcium content (7.4 g kg⁻¹). The collection consists of 48 cultivars of different origin and provenance (Table 1). According to recent findings, 'Montebello', 'Nocchione' and 'Santa Maria del Gesù' are synonyms (Bocacci et al., 2006). Each accession in the collection is represented by three multi-stemmed plants planted at a spacing of 4m x 5m, each trained as an open vase, irrigated through a sub-irrigation system and managed with standard orchard management techniques and an integrated pest management plan. Phenology, vigour and productivity of each cultivar were observed over a three year period (2014-2016).

Phenology, vigour and productivity

Time of flowering, recorded as the start and end of male and female full bloom, leaf budbreak, and leaf fall of each cultivar were recorded weekly according to Germaine (1994). The number of suckers and vigour of the trees were also measured. Further, nut yield and nut and kernel traits were investigated. The vegetative growth for each cultivar was determined as trunk cross-sectional area (TCA) measured during the last vegetative season at 30 cm above the ground (September 2016) and expressed as the sum of the TCAs of each trunk. Yield efficiency (EF) was calculated as ratio between the yield recorded in the year 2016 and TCA (EF= yield TCA⁻¹). Sucker emission was rated yearly on a five-point scale (very low, low, medium, high, very high). Nut and kernel traits and kernel/nut ratio (% kernel) were calculated on sub-samples of 100 nuts for each cultivar according to De Salvador et al., (2005).

Statistical analysis

Analysis of variance was performed on the data collected to estimate the effects of cultivar and year and their interaction using the SYSTAT MGLH procedure (Wilkinson, 1998). The least significant difference (L.S.D. p=0.05) for the comparison of the means was then calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vigour and production

The cultivars showed a wide range in number of suckers as in a previous study (Cristofori et al., 2014). 'Barcelona', 'Napoletanedda', 'Riccia di Talanico' and 'Tonda di Giffoni' had a "very high" number of suckers, while the 'Heynick's Zellernuss' showed a "low" number and 'Pallagrossa', 'Closca Molla' and 'Corford' a "very low" number (data not shown).

The cultivars showed also a range in plant vigour quantified as TAC (Table 1). The values ranged from 337 cm² in 'Montebello' to 2,551 cm² in 'Pallagrossa'. High vigour (>1,500 cm²) was also seen in 'Daviana', 'Grifoll' and 'Segorbe', while low vigour (<500 cm²) was seen in 'Napoletanedda' and 'Karidaty'.

Nut yields (2014-2016) were expressed as kg of dry, in-shell nuts per tree and tons per hectare. 'Camponica' was the most productive cultivar with an average yield of 6.50 kg tree⁻¹ (3.25 t ha⁻¹). High yield (>5 kg tree⁻¹ and >2.5 t ha⁻¹) was also observed in 'Barrettona', 'Carello', 'Nocchione', 'Nociara', 'Piazza Armerina', 'San Giovanni', 'S.M. del Gesù', 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'Tonda Gentile Romana'. On average, 2014 showed low yields caused by frost damage at the time of leaf budbreak, while yields were higher and similar in 2015 and 2016. 'Bearn' and 'Heynick's Zellernuss' were the least productive (average annual yield < 1.50 kg tree⁻¹). The highest yield efficiency (YE) in 2016 was for 'Nociara' (0.011), and the lowest for 'Pallagrossa' (0.001) (Table 1). Two cultivars from Sicily ('Minnolara' and 'S.M. del Gesù') and two from Campania ('Camponica' and 'Avellana Speciale') showed high YE in 2016.

A broad range of values was observed also for the nut and kernel traits (Table 1). Percent kernel ranged from 34% in 'Bearn' to 51% in 'Napoletanedda'. High percent kernel (>47%) was observed in the round Italian cultivars 'Tonda di Giffoni', 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe' and 'Tonda Gentile Romana' as well as 'Camponica', 'Daviana', 'Grifoll' and 'San Giovanni'.

Phenological traits

Phenological observations were conducted over three years. Date of leaf budbreak was recorded as when over 50% of terminal buds were enlarged and the bud scales had opened to expose the green of the leaves inside. Leaf budbreak in 2015 was one-two weeks earlier than in 2016 and 2017. The earliest budbreak was observed in 'San Giovanni' and 'Tonda di Giffoni', followed by 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe' and 'Karidaty' (first half of February). This marked early date could expose the young leaves to frost damage. The latest budbreak (second half of March - beginning of April) was noted in 'Apolda', 'Bearn', 'Cosford', 'Pallagrossa', 'Heynick's Zellernuss' and 'Segorbe' (data not shown). On average, leaf budbreak occurred about one month earlier than in Slovenia (Solar and Stampar, 2011).

Leaf drop occurred two weeks later in 2014 than in 2015 and 2016. Most leaves dropped between November and the first half of December. The earliest leaf drop was observed in 'Cosford', 'Daviana', 'Negret', and 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe' (first half of November) and the latest was observed in 'Camponica', 'Comen', 'Tonda di Giffoni' and 'San Giovanni'.

Flowering times are presented for each of three years in Figure 1. 'Tonda Rossa', 'Karidaty', 'Sivri A' and 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe' showed very early pollen shed, which was concentrated in mid-December. The pollen shedding time was consistent for 'Tonda Gentile delle Langhe' over the three years of observation. Early pollen shed was also noted in 'Segorbe', 'Tonda di Giffoni', and 'Pallagrossa'. 'Morell', 'Pallagrossa', 'Tonda Gentile Romana', 'Heynick's Zellernuss' and 'Longue d'Espagne' were the latest to shed pollen, concentrated in the first half of February. The earliest female bloom was noted in 'Barcelona', 'Nostrale', 'San Giovanni' and 'Tonda di Giffoni', which reached style emergence (red-dot stage) at the end of November. Early female full bloom (late December - early January) was also observed in 'Iannusa Racinante', 'Comune di Sicilia', 'Nociara', 'Nostrale', followed by 'Barrettona', 'Camponica' and 'Tonda di Giffoni'. The latest female full bloom was recorded for 'Cosford', 'Heynick's Zellernuss', 'Longue d'Espagne' and 'Pallagrossa' (end February - early March). Homogamy was also recorded for 'Iannusa Racinante', 'Avellana Speciale', 'Barrettona' and partially for 'Comune di Sicilia', 'Nociara', 'Nostrale' and 'Racinante', mainly characterized by a early-medium full bloom period. The most widely

planted cultivar in Latium orchards ('Tonda Gentile Romana') showed a medium-late full bloom (end of January - early February) and showed also a tendency of homogamy (Figure 1c). Due to sporophytic incompatibility, not all hazelnut cultivars can serve as pollinizers for each other (Mehlenbacher, 1997).

CONCLUSIONS

'Heynick's Zellernuss', 'Pallagrossa' and 'Cosford' showed very few suckers, and 'Heynick's Zellernuss' has moderate vigour. The highest yields during the three years of investigation were for 'Barrettona', 'Camponica', 'Nociara' and 'San Giovanni', suggesting their use for the enlargement of the genetic base of hazelnut plantings in Latium. Further investigations will be useful to identify suitable cultivars for renewal of older orchards in Latium and the planting of new orchards.

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Table

Table 1. Cultivars origin, plant yield, yield ha⁻¹ (average of three years), cumulative yield, trunk cross-sectional area (TCA recorded at 30 cm above the ground in 2016), yield efficiency (EF detected in 2016), and percent kernel of the cultivars present in the collection field located at “Le Cese” (Viterbo, Italy) (TG=Tonda di Giffoni; TGDL=Tonda Gentile delle Langhe; TGR=Tonda Gentile Romana).

CULTIVAR	Origin	Yield Average 2014-16 (Kg tree ⁻¹)	Yield Σ 2014-16 (Kg tree ⁻¹)	Yield Average 2014-16 (ton ha ⁻¹)	TCA 2016 (cm ²)	EF 2016 (Kg cm ² ⁻¹)	% Kernel
Ian. Racinante	Sicily (IT)	3.95	11.86	1.97	611.90	0.006	41.64
Apolda	Unknown	2.25	6.76	1.13	652.09	0.004	42.44
Av. Speciale	Campania (IT)	4.91	14.75	2.45	659.32	0.008	39.11
Barcelona	France	5.32	15.96	2.66	1311.26	0.005	42.19
Barrettona	Unknown	5.67	17.02	2.83	922.94	0.006	38.66
Bearn	Unknown	1.49	4.48	0.75	688.61	0.002	33.86
Camponica	Campania (IT)	6.50	19.51	3.25	911.54	0.008	47.43
Carrello	Sicily (IT)	6.21	18.63	3.10	1140.14	0.006	38.53
Closca Molla	Spain	1.81	5.42	0.90	651.84	0.003	46.94
Comen	Greece	2.35	7.06	1.18	822.94	0.003	46.49
Com. di Sicilia	Sicily (IT)	3.44	10.34	1.72	945.94	0.004	35.28
Cosford	England	2.91	8.74	1.45	1211.08	0.003	42.48
Daviana	England	2.57	7.71	1.28	1775.51	0.002	47.48
Ennis	USA	3.37	10.13	1.69	1250.67	0.003	35.43
Fructo Rubro	Unknown	4.47	13.41	2.23	1378.57	0.003	40.73
Gironell	Spain	4.30	12.90	2.15	1298.91	0.004	41.44
Grifoll	Spain	2.30	6.91	1.15	1722.73	0.002	49.62
Grossal	Unknown	3.82	11.46	1.91	722.37	0.006	41.00
Gunslebert	Germany	3.93	11.80	1.97	796.18	0.005	41.91
Heynick's Zel.	Unknown	1.49	4.48	0.75	969.22	0.002	38.28
Jean's	England	2.40	7.20	1.20	894.59	0.003	43.18
Karidaty	Turkey	1.80	5.40	0.90	465.94	0.005	43.88
L. d'Espagna	England	2.31	6.95	1.15	833.77	0.003	41.71
Merveille Bol.	France	3.55	10.66	1.78	621.24	0.006	44.79
Minnolara	Sicily (IT)	4.72	14.16	2.36	557.33	0.009	39.50
Montebello	Sicily (IT)	1.56	4.68	0.78	336.39	0.005	37.28
Morell	Spain	4.05	12.17	2.03	833.77	0.005	43.72
Napoletanedda	Sicily (IT)	1.54	4.62	0.77	346.82	0.005	51.62
Negret	Spain	1.59	4.77	0.80	917.23	0.002	42.35
Nocchione	Latium (IT)	5.56	16.70	2.78	850.14	0.007	38.23
Nociara	Sicily (IT)	6.10	18.29	3.05	575.94	0.011	37.63
Nostrale	Sicily (IT)	4.73	14.19	2.36	992.79	0.005	38.51
Pallagrossa	Unknown	2.00	6.00	1.00	2551.04	0.001	39.50
P. Armerina	Sicily (IT)	5.21	15.63	2.60	850.14	0.007	38.24
Racinante	Sicily (IT)	4.60	13.80	2.30	963.38	0.005	37.77
R. Talanico	Campania (IT)	4.34	13.02	2.17	1331.78	0.004	43.46
San Giovanni	Campania (IT)	6.08	18.44	3.04	1127.47	0.006	47.90
S.M. del Gesù	Sicily (IT)	5.02	15.07	2.51	616.56	0.008	36.04
Segorbe	France	2.75	8.27	1.38	1597.89	0.002	42.96
Sivri "A"	Turkey	4.13	12.41	2.07	683.69	0.007	41.27
Tombul	Turkey	1.80	5.40	0.90	539.71	0.004	46.27
Tonda Bianca	Campania (IT)	2.80	8.40	1.40	733.76	0.004	34.46
TG	Campania (IT)	5.00	15.00	2.50	1401.31	0.004	44.05
TGDL	Piedmont (IT)	2.00	6.01	1.00	1324.92	0.002	44.11

TGR	Latium (IT)	5.44	16.32	2.72	945.94	0.007	45.52
Tonda Rossa	Campania (IT)	2.33	7.00	1.16	566.25	0.006	46.93
Vermellett	Unknown	3.10	9.30	1.55	1198.02	0.003	41.82
Vermellett "SP"	Unknown	1.60	4.81	0.80	566.25	0.004	40.34
L.S.D. (P=0.05)							
Cultivar (C)		0.04	0.51	0.02	295.98	n.s.	3.43
Year (Y)		0.16	-	0.08	-	-	0.70
C x Y		0.28	-	0.14	-	-	4.85

Figures

Figure 1a - Description of flowering phenogram of hazelnut used for describing the flowering of cultivars in figure 1b and 1c. "Beginning" indicates the period when the red-dot stage appears on female flowers and few have extended stigmas, and when catkins start to elongate and few have pollen shedding. The "dot" indicates the peak of flowering (50% of flowers are open). The "shaded histogram" indicates the window of full bloom. "End" indicates the last part of flowering where only few female flowers are still receptive and few catkins are still shedding pollen.

Figure 1b - Dates of flowering observed in the first group of accessions (24 cultivars) at Viterbo (Italy) during the three-year of investigation (flowering season 2014-15; 2015-16; 2016-17).

Figure 1c - Dates of flowering observed in the second group of accessions (24 cultivars) at Viterbo (Italy) during the three-years of investigation (flowering season 2014-15; 2015-16; 2016-17).

